

A study on Stress Management in the Workplace

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 30 July 2018

Keywords

Stress, Workplace, psychological, physiological

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ABSTRACT

Stress has been recognized as one of the major issues in the workplace. Stress refers to a state of psychological and physiological imbalance resulting from the difference between situational demand and the individual ability to meet those needs. The purpose of this study is to investigate the causes of stress and to highlight the consequences arise from stress. It also gives importance on the ways to measure and manage stress in the workplace. The study found that stress is a fact and indeed a common problem to any type of people but of the different types and it can be alleviate if one knows how to take good care of himself and his surroundings.

1. Introduction

Stress is a common problem that affects almost all of us at some point in our lives. It happens to many people every day in our lives. Knowing how to identify when you are under stress, what makes you stress, and different ways of coping with stress can greatly improve both your mental and physical wellbeing. When we use the word stress we feel that everything appears to own become an excessive amount, we tend to wonder if we actually cope with the pressures placed upon us. Something that poses a challenge or a threat to our well-being could be a stress. Sometimes stress is good for one as it encourages and motivates them to get going. Imagine a life without stress, it will be boring as there will be no challenges and proper goals for every individual in the workplace but too much of stress or excessive work can disturb a person's mental and physical wellbeing. In the workplace, stress will have an effect on performance. Employees with less stress might not create enough effort to perform at their best levels, whereas those employees with too much of stress typically are unable to concentrate or perform effectively and efficiently.

Stress may be a fact in our everyday life. Once someone needs help, it means that the person feels physically and showing emotion disabled. Most of the people believe that their capability and capabilities are very little to encounter high level of stress. Today, human is associate in a transition method from an industrial to a post- industrial world. Also, the post- industrial world, just like the agricultural or industrial world has its own characteristics. People were living their own simple life over thousands of years; however industrial revolution began to change their life in numerous aspects. (Bahamian et. Al 2012).

In a workplace, stress may arise due to many reasons such as working for a long period of time, heavy workload, pressure to complete a task within a short period of time, sudden changes in the workplace, lack of skills to do the job, discrimination and harassment etc. This badly affects the employees in the workplace. When an employee is affected, it directly or indirectly affects the organisation in the form of job performance, employee's satisfaction, and decrease in retention rate. Therefore the need for management of stress is very

essential to every organisation. The better the management of stress better is the organisational management.

2. Review of Literature

Eisen et al. (2008) found that the frequency of skills practice, independent of the intervention format, predicts stress reduction. Traditionally, stress-management interventions have been similar to the one described in the current investigation, a classroom type of format where the majority of the intervention involves a "teacher" giving pre-made lectures to groups of "students." Use of blended learning techniques (combining technological approaches with experiential education) may prove to be an especially effective tool for personalizing interventions and providing opportunities for self-directed learning.

NIOSH identifies some job and work stress trends that will occur within the next decade as follows: (1) nine out of 10 new jobs will be in the service sector, which has been shown to pose increased risk of psychological disorders; (2) six of every 10 new jobs will be filled by women whose multiple role demands and constrained economic opportunities may put them at a high risk for psychological disorders; (3) computers and robots may affect as many as seven million factory jobs and 38 million office jobs, which can lead to stressors such as job displacement and lower-paying jobs; (4) health service occupations, such as nurses and nurses' aides, are among the fastest growing occupations and have consistently been found to be at risk for psychological disorders (Hatfield, 1990). Given these trends and the mounting costs of stress, undertaking steps to tolerate, reduce, and eliminate environmental demands is critical.

Mimura & Griffiths (2003) concluded that there is more evidence for the effectiveness of personal support than environmental management for reducing workplace stress in the nursing profession. However, it is not possible at this stage to determine what kind of approach is more effective, because the number of studies is too small to compare different approaches.

Ethnic minority employees, resembling Black Americans and Hispanics, have been known as being more subjected to stress

strictly due to their background (Keita & Jones, 1990). Stress level among the women has also been studied. It's wide believed that women as a group are more stressed and feel completely different stress than men. (Chusmir & Franks, 1988; Cooke & Rousseau, 1984; Gadzella et al., 1990). Jick and Mitz (1985) urged that women experience psychological stress (e.g., depression, emotional discomfort) a lot of often than men, who tend to experience a lot of physiological stress than women (e.g., coronary cardiovascular disease, cirrhosis of the liver of the liver). A number of these variations in stress levels are often attributed to the socialization method of men and women, that brings regarding completely different perceptions of the workplace (Chusmir & Franks, 1988). Women are also expected to hold the burden of raising the kids and acting family chores while making the house that will increase stress levels (Chusmir & Franks, 1988; Cooke & Rousseau, 1984). Levi (1981) has indicated that two to three times as many women than men are chronic worriers. To mention more, women typically suffer from stress because of work underload wherever under-promotion results in women being clustered at the lower levels of the many organizations (Keita & Jones, 1990).

3. Meaning and Definition of Stress

Zajacova et al. (2005) state that stress refers to the non-specific response of the body, to something that produces an individual feels vulnerable or upset. Stress prepares the body to satisfy things that measure powerful with focus, stamina and strength. It will be caused by positive or dangerous experiences. Stress is aggravated by events known as stressors. There are two types of stress. Negative stress (distress) and positive stress (eustress). Eustress affects our activities during a positive means (Striker et al., 1999). It's a short stress that will increase the body's strength instantly. Positive stress affects people during the times of physical activity, excitement or creativeness. It motivates an individual to end a particular task and helps one assume critically towards an assignment (Spector, 2002). Negative stress is that the most well liked kind of stress. It arises once the conventional routine of the body is altered. It causes negative effects equivalent to anxiety, depression, fatigue and unhappiness. Once an individual is distressed, the body becomes unable to come to a relaxed state even once the stressors are absent.

According to Cropanzano et al., (1997), Stress is a mental feeling when job duties are beyond person's capabilities. These mental feelings create the anxiety and tension which are symptoms of stress.

"The National Job Safety and Health Institution" defined job stress as an annoying excitement which occurs when there is no proportion between person's wants, job requirements, and person's talents, or worker's resources and needs.

4. Causes of Stress

The major causes of stress at the workplace are as follows:

1. Long period of time
2. Heavy workload
3. Pressure to complete a task within a short period of time
4. Sudden changes in the workplace

5. Lack of skills to do the job
6. Discrimination and harassment
7. Lack of social support
8. Career concern
9. Poor working condition
10. Lack of employees cohesiveness

5. Consequences of Stress

Consequence of stress can be discussed into two ways-

Individual Level Consequences

1. Poor individual performance (e.g., job performance, skills and communication, employees participation in vital roles)
2. Poor psychological and psychological state outcomes (e.g., anger, depression, anxiety, posttraumatic stress syndrome, burnout, etc.)
3. Impaired physiological processes (e.g., cardiovascular reactivity, elevated levels of assorted hormones, impaired immune function)
4. Physical illness outcomes (e.g., high blood pressure, stroke, cancer, headaches, migraine)
5. Detrimental activity outcomes (sleep disturbance; alcohol, tobacco, and illicit drug use; poor consumption habits; intimate partner violence)

Organization Level Consequences

1. Poor psychological and emotional outcomes (e.g., job discontentedness, low structure commitment)
2. Indicators of poor physical health (absence due to sickness, workers' compensation claims)
3. Work-related activity impairment (injuries, poor job performance, poor productivity, on-the-job substance use)

6. Stress management at workplace

Managing an employee who worked for long hour and stressed human resource became a difficult and ever tough task for today's managers. With an aim to utilize the accessible human resource thus minimizing costs and increasing profits, nowadays each manager and their subordinates have to be compelled to coop with work connected stress. This stress if it goes to sure extent while not being controlled will have an effect on the person's family/social life, health, performance etc. and changes the employee's whole perspective towards work-frustrating, demotivating and horrifying him/her that within the long run damages the organization and also the worker each.

7. Strategies to Counter Stress in Workplace

Organizational plans: This type of plans is performed through current organisational mechanisms. For example, well-designed and regular jobs will scale back job stress.

Side Plans: Side plans as well as organisational proceedings are useful for stress reduction in several organizations. For an example, for employee's health promotion program, nowadays, most organizations are attempting to produce exceptional aspect plans or to use the existing programs.

8. Stress prevention Strategy

It is not possible to come up with an answer to stop stress; however we are able to give several suggestions instead. To acknowledge these issues, first of all, we've got to treat size and therefore the available resources of the organization. Despite the tactic of data gathering, data ought to embrace workers understanding of their operating conditions, stress level, health and satisfaction. The list of the operating condition, which can result in stress and warning signs of stress and impact, may be a decent begin to make decision on collected data (Alipour, 2011, p. 34).

In the next stage, when recognizing stress resources and understanding its aspects, plan and execution of intervention strategy is adjusted. In a workplace where employees are less, official discussions might create helpful concepts on prevention that facilitate to recognise stress difficulties. Whereas in a bigger workplace, an official process will be required. Some interferences could also be performed quickly, (such as improvement of communications, education etc.) whereas some others might need more time (Alipour, 2011, p. 34).

Following habits will remarkably facilitate to alleviate stress:

- Regular practice of meditation in everyday life
- Regular physical exercise
- Maintaining balanced diet
- Focused thinking on the job and career

- Control of temper
- Managing depression in the workplace as well as outside the workplace
- Maintaining calmness in any type of situation that can lead to stress
- Having a positive angle towards life
- Harmony towards self and other

9. Conclusion

It can be concluded that stress is a fact that can happen to anyone at any time in any place. However the level of stress may differ according to the situation and the type of people. Stress at workplace is common to every organisation irrespective of the level of employees but there is a way to manage stress depending upon the individual life style and the organisation he or she belongs. It is found that the level of stress is high to employees who are more under pressure and to people who are unable to control their personal life. Therefore there is a need for conducting a workshop and seminars related to stress management in the workplace in order to manage stress among the employees. Managers should create an environment which is participative culture and give certain freedom to the employees according to their type of job which will help the employees to work effectively and efficiently. So the study is of paramount importance as it highlights several important issues for stress management the practice of human resource management in the workplace.

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